

SPORTS ACTIVITY AND ITS DEVELOPMENT

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Annotation: This article analyzes the necessity and social importance of an innovative approach to the development of physical culture. developing a healthy lifestyle among young people is also one of the important tasks. The young generation is very susceptible to various influences. During this period, the conscious personal activity necessary for the formation of a healthy lifestyle is perfected.

Key words: sports games, sports culture, healthy life, pledge of the future, constantly healthy.

In order to increase the popularity of physical education and sports in our republic to a higher level, develop the movement of Physical Culture, revive the national games of the people, form a healthy lifestyle, train talented athletes in modern sports and improve their sports skills, many of the decrees and decisions adopted by the first president of our country Islam Karimov have become important in popularizing and Since the early days of independence, our country has formed a certain legal framework for implementing self-imposed reforms in this area. In particular, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan" on the organization of the activities of the children's Sports Development Fund of Uzbekistan", order of the people's Ministry of education of the Republic of Uzbekistan" on improving the staffing of children's and youth sports schools", in 2007" on approval of the budget of the children's Sports Development Fund, The decision of the Cabinet of Ministers" on the organization of activities of the foundation for the development of Physical Culture and sports under the Ministry of Physical Culture and sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan", the adoption of official regulatory documents such as the decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan" on measures for the further development of Physical Education and mass sports " led to the.

One of the first works of the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov to introduce Uzbekistan and Uzbek sport to the world in the early years of independence was the opening of the "President's Cup" international tournament in Tashkent on August 29, 1995. On March 5, 2018, the decree of our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev "on measures to radically improve the system of Public Administration in the field of Physical Education and sports" was adopted. In accordance with the decree, on the basis of the previous state committee and its territorial divisions, the Ministry of physical education and sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established, its functions and powers were expanded. On September 20, 2018, a meeting was held by the head of the country dedicated to the issues of development of the field of physical education and sports. It noted that the introduction of a new system for improving the selection – selection work of athletes gave its initial results. We are proud of our athletes who have made a significant contribution to

increasing the prestige and prestige of Uzbekistan in international sports fields. At the same time, we should pay great attention to mass sports, not limited to the achievements in high Sports, "said the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at this meeting. Until independence, Uzbekistan was closed to the international sports community in old age. International competitions in our country practically did not take place, except for tournaments in football and tennis with the participation of athletes from former socialist states.

Positive politics also left its complications in the field of physical education and sports, which were especially manifested in the following:

1. In Uzbekistan, physical education and sports work was established at a relatively low level compared to the central republics, the movement of sports was not engaged in the mass of the local population, and there was no clear and purposeful work on the training of highly qualified athletes from among them.

2. The development of sports networks, the construction of sports facilities, the expansion and financing of the material and technical base of sports in general were carried out in a limited way, only with the consent of the center.

3. Although the training of higher and Secondary Education personnel for the field was established, national athlete personnel at competitions were forced to undergo various artificial obstacles and qualifiers.

As soon as Independence was achieved, in January 1992, the law "on Physical Education and sports" was adopted, the legal basis for the development of physical education and sports in the country. In the short term: - the organizational basis for the management of physical education and sports was improved; - the National Olympic Committee of Uzbekistan, federations for sports were established; national types of physical education, wellness, mass sports work and sports were developed; - the material and technical base of physical education and sports was strengthened; training and retraining of personnel in the field of physical education and sports are carried out according to the National Education Program.

In order to ensure the physical and spiritual perfection of the younger generation in our country, in order to develop a healthy lifestyle and love for sports, to create a material base of children's sports in places, to create a material base of children's sports in populated areas, and to further activate the work of providing sports equipment and equipment, in The president of the Republic of Uzbekistan was elected chairman of the foundation's sponsorship board. The chairman of Zhukori Kenges of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the governors of the regions and the city of Tashkent were appointed as the presidents of the councils of khominism of regional branches. In order to organize the mass, continuous involvement of students in sports activities, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted in 2003 "on the organization of a system of continuous sports competitions aimed at attracting students and student youth to sports." On the basis of this decision, the country has established a plan for holding Republican final stages in the regions of the competitions "NIH of Hope", "harmonious generation", "Universiade" of students of secondary schools, academic lyceums and vocational colleges and higher education institutions.

Particular attention is paid to this area, taking into account the fact that regular exercise in physical education and sports plays an important role in strengthening the health

of our population, first of all, of our younger generation. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev carries out a number of measures and measures in order to develop the sports sector in our state, as a result of which the national sports teams of Uzbekistan occupy high positions in the competitions held at the Asian and world level. In this regard, on February 15, 2017, the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan was published on measures to further improve the management system in the field of Culture and sports. According to the first paragraph of this decree, the Ministry of Culture and sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan will be liquidated, and on its basis: – the Ministry of culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan; – the state committee of Physical Culture and sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan will be established.

In accordance with the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the main tasks and directions of activity of the state committee of Physical Education and sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan were determined. On October 31, 2017, under the chairmanship of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, a meeting was held on the issues of improving the management system in the field of physical education and sports, development of mass sports, selection and education of talented athletes, strengthening the field with qualified personnel and building modern sports facilities. At this meeting, the president of our country Shavkat Mirziyoyev gave a speech and said in his speeches, large-scale work on this was carried out in the years of independence. The necessary conditions were created for the regular participation of the population, especially the younger generation, in physical education and mass sports. Modern sports complexes were built in cities and villages. The competitions "sprouts of hope", "harmonious generation" and "Universiade" have become a means of introducing young people to mass sports, a healthy lifestyle. A continuous system for the selection of talented children and the training of professional athletes was created. Boys and girls, whose abilities are conspicuous in training in public schools and children's sports complexes, are taken to children's and youth sports schools, sports colleges and brought up on professional approaches. Thanks to this, the athletes of our country have achieved high victories in prestigious World competitions and show the potential of our people to the whole world. In particular, our athletes won 13 medals at the 2016 Olympic Games in Brazil and 31 medals at the Paralympic Games, the highest in the history of the sport of our country. The decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on measures for the further development of Physical Education and mass sports" of June 3, 2017 was another important document in the field. With this decision, a program for the further development of physical education and mass sports was adopted in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The program will spend more than 995.2 billion for the further development of physical education and mass sports in 2017-2021, build, reconstruct, overhaul, equip and re-equip 167 sports facilities, including 90 sports complexes and 77 swimming pools, in order to strengthen the material and technical base of sports schools. Within the framework of the program, 153 children's fields were completed in the current year, 232 modern fields, a specialized sports complex for Olympic and national sports in the city of Nukus. The meeting also pointed out the shortcomings allowed in this regard. In particular, it was criticized that the construction and reconstruction of 39 sports facilities at the expense of the children's Sports Development Fund lagged behind the schedule, and the equipment of swimming pools with modern facilities was delayed. Tasks were given to eliminate these shortcomings, to complete the construction work by the end of the year. It

was noted that it is necessary to increase the efficiency of the use of sports complexes, to attract young people more widely to them. The cooperation of sports schools, higher sports skills schools of the Republic and sports federations on the discovery of talented young people, selection work has not been established on demand. In this regard, instructions were given to create a clear transparent mechanism and cover all regions.

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